

Evaluation of *in vitro* bioactivity profile of bee propolis extracts delivered by yeast glucan particles

Adéla Brejchová^{a,1} , Petra Třešňáková^b,
Giyallah Habibullah^b , Jitka Viktorová^b,
Denisa Lizoňová^{a,*}

^a University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Chemical Engineering, Technická 3, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic

^b University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, Technická 3, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic

^c University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Food Analysis and Nutrition, Technická 3, Prague 6, 166 28, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Due to its antibacterial, anticancer and immunomodulatory properties, propolis is widely used in the treatment of various diseases. However, its poor water solubility and bioavailability reduce its effectiveness *in vivo*. A solution may be found by combining enhanced propolis extraction with loading the extract into a suitable carrier. Here, we investigated glucan particles, obtained from the cell walls of baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*), as promising porous carriers capable of increasing the dispersion of propolis and, thereby, its solubility. First, propolis extracts were prepared using a modified sonication method (70 % ethanol at a propolis/ethanol ratio of 1:10); three types of raw propolis differing in source location and year of harvest were used for comparison. Next, lyophilized propolis extracts were loaded into the glucan particles by spray drying and slurry evaporation to ensure the resulting propolis extract content of 10 wt %. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy and SEM confirmed the successful loading into the glucan particles, and UV-VIS spectrophotometry was used to determine encapsulation efficiency. Dissolution tests showed that the loading into glucan particles led to the formation of a supersaturated solution of propolis extract and the enhancement of its dissolution rate. Subsequently, the biological activity of the encapsulated propolis extract was investigated. Overall, the encapsulated propolis extract showed much higher anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antimicrobial activity than pure propolis. Thus, our results indicate that the combination of propolis extract with glucan particles increases propolis solubility and bioactivity.

1. Introduction

Propolis is a resinous substance produced by honeybees (*Apis mellifera* L.) to protect their hives from diseases caused by fungi, yeast, and bacteria [1–3]. Propolis composition varies depending on its geographic location and the plants from which it is collected but typically consists of more than 850 chemical components [4,5], mostly flavonoids, phenols, and essential oils [6]. These include, for example: chrysin, apigenin, kaempferol, quercetin, pinocembrin, galangin, 10-hydroxyl-2-decenoic acid, and cinnamic acid.

Chrysin is a potent flavone known for its strong anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties [7,8]. It reduces the inflammation of the immune system, thereby decreasing damage caused by macrophages,

neutrophils, and other immune-inflammatory reactions. Chrysin also lowers levels of TNF α , IL-12, and IL-6 and downregulates pro inflammatory enzymes such as COX-2 and NO synthase [7]. *Apigenin* is a flavone notable for its potential anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects. It induces apoptosis, inhibits cell proliferation, and blocks angiogenesis in various cancer lines. Apigenin also reduces inflammation by inhibiting the COX-2 and modulating NF- κ B signaling, which decreases IL-8 and TNF α production [9,10]. *Kaempferol*, a flavonol, exhibits significant antioxidant activity and has been associated with reduced risk of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease and cancer [11,12]. *Quercetin*, one of the most abundant flavonoids in the human diet, is known for its anti-inflammatory, antihistamine, and antiviral properties [12,13]. *Pinocembrin*, a flavanone found

* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: Denisa.Lizonova@vscht.cz (D. Lizoňová), Frantisek.Stepanek@vscht.cz (F. Štěpánek).

¹ Equal contribution.

prominently in propolis, is well-recognized for its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities. By inhibiting the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, pinocembrin effectively promotes wound healing and combats infections, making it a valuable therapeutic compound [12]. *Galangin*, is a flavonol distinguished by its antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects, protecting cells from oxidative damage and inhibiting the growth of various pathogens [14,15]. *10-hydroxyl-2-decenoic acid* is a fatty acid derivative known for its immunomodulatory effects, promoting the proliferation of immune cells and enhancing host defense mechanisms [16]. *Cinnamic acid* is a phenolic compound with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. It has been investigated for its potential in preventing oxidative stress-related diseases [17].

Thus, propolis has very promising therapeutic potential, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial activities [2,3]. However, it also has unfavorable physicochemical properties which, together with its inherent chemical variability, limit its direct application due to poor solubility and bioavailability [18].

Propolis cannot be used as a raw material, that's why purification by extraction is usually employed [19]. Extraction of propolis is the most popular technique with the use of various types of solvents such as ethanol, glycerin, propylene glycol, and polyethylene glycol [20]. The most popular one is ethanolic extraction, which is simple and effective while rich in biologically active compounds and obtaining none or low amounts of wax [3,19].

To overcome limitations regarding its strong flavor, poor solubility, and low bioavailability, encapsulation techniques are frequently employed [21–23]. Encapsulation is a process of enclosing the active ingredient into a suitable carrier to protect or improve the properties of the active ingredient. Of the available encapsulation techniques, spray drying appears to be one of the best options because of its wide availability of equipment, low processing cost, and final product stability and quality [24,25]. Moreover, spray drying has previously been used with success for producing amorphous solid dispersions, thereby enhancing solubility and absorption of poorly soluble drugs [21,26].

Several papers have described the spray-dried encapsulation of propolis extract in various carriers. The most widely used carriers are maltodextrins, vinal gum/Arabic gum, and inulin [22,25,27]. Maltodextrins are commonly used for their low viscosity, high water solubility, high bioactive compound retention and good protection of the active ingredient against oxidation [21,22,25,28,29]. Nevertheless, their low emulsifying capacity is a big limitation for poorly water-soluble molecules [22,25]. The use of gums has been shown to change the release kinetics in encapsulation systems. They have good emulsifying ability in aqueous solutions and are odorless and tasteless [22,30,31]. However, the use of such a substance on its own does not provide sufficient protection of the active ingredient [22]. Inulin is known for its prebiotic and dietary fiber effects, and low cost, but its use is hampered by its poor water solubility and low encapsulation efficiency [22,25,32]. More recently, interest has turned to biocompatible drug carriers from natural sources, particularly glucan particles, whose own biological activity could be beneficial [33].

As carriers, glucan particles can promote immunomodulatory effects by interacting with the immune system through Peyer's patches located in the gut [34–36]. These polysaccharides can be inexpensively and easily obtained from the cell walls of baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) which consist mainly of (1,3)- β -D-glucan and (1,6)- β -D-glucan in side chains [33,37,38]. As they are living organisms, consistently produced under controlled conditions [37], the size of the yeast cells is highly conserved ($5.1 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$ [39]). Glucan particles are porous, inherently insoluble in ethanol and aqueous media but are partially hydrophilic and easily dispersed in water [40]. Furthermore, the encapsulation of poorly soluble compounds in glucan particles has been shown to improve their dissolution properties [40], and protect against evaporation, oxidation and light [27]. Yet, no study has investigated the encapsulation of propolis extract in yeast glucan particles.

Here, we encapsulate propolis extracts in glucan particles by spray drying in order to improve their bioactivity and dissolution properties. In *in vitro* tests, we study the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial potential of three different propolis samples and compare it to the composites obtained by loading the propolis extracts into the glucan particles. We show that the method of propolis extract delivery employing glucan particles has great potential for its direct application to treat infections and promote wound healing.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Three different samples of propolis were collected. The first sample (PP 1) was collected in the Czech Republic, Česká Lípa, 2018. Other samples were collected in Prague (Czech Republic) in the years 2020 (PP 2) and 2021 (PP 3).

Instant baker's yeast, S.I. Lesaffre (France), was purchased from a local grocery shop. Hydrochloric acid, phosphoric acid, acetone, and isopropanol were from Lach-Ner (Czech Republic). Sodium hydroxide, sodium dihydrogen phosphate dihydrate, methanol and ethanol were from Penta (Czech Republic). Sodium dodecyl sulfate was from Sigma-Aldrich (USA).

Standards of 8 substances of interest, in terms of biological activity, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA): 10-hydroxyl-2-decenoic acid, cinnamic acid, chrysin, apigenin, kaempferol, quercetin, pinocembrin, galangin.

Deionized water was obtained from a Milli-Q purification system supplied by Millipore (USA), HPLC grade methanol from Honeywell (Germany), formic acid from VWR Chemicals (Great Britain), ammonium formate from Merck (Germany) and APCI Positive and Negative Calibration Solutions for the SCIEX X500 System from SCIEX (Canada).

TNF alpha Monoclonal Antibody (14-7423-85), TNF alpha Polyclonal Antibody, Biotin (13-7341-85), IL-6 Monoclonal Antibody (14-7061-85), IL-6 Monoclonal Antibody, Biotin (13-7062-85), Avidin and HRP conjugate (434423) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (USA) 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine Liquid Substrate (T4319), Griess reagent (modified; G4410) and Resazurin sodium salt were from Merck (Germany).

2.2. Collection of propolis

Propolis was collected from one of the authors' (F.Š.) own bees (*Apis mellifera carnica*, descendants of mother no. CCZ KR1 180201, with morphometric analyses K7821-K7824), stationed at Prague - Hodkovičky (235 m.a.s.l., beekeeping station reg. no. CZ 90217199) characterised mainly by decorative park and forest trees, garden fruit trees and garden flowers. Samples from the 2020 and 2021 seasons were used. Both seasons were characterized by typical Central European summer weather, with no anomalies in temperature or precipitation.

2.3. Preparation of dry ethanolic extract of propolis

For the propolis extraction, a modified combination of methods published by Khacha-ananda et al. [41] and Pobiega et al. [42] was used. First, crude propolis was frozen with liquid nitrogen and crushed with a pestle to obtain fine particles and facilitate material processing. Then, a solution of propolis in 70 % ethanol (ratio 1:10) was prepared and stirred (300 rpm) overnight, in the dark, at 30 °C. Then, the solution was sonicated for 30 min and cleared of particulate impurities by centrifugation (5000 rpm, 10 min). The solution was cooled in the fridge for a couple of hours and filtrated using Whatman® qualitative filter paper, Grade 1 (cellulose filters, 11 μm). To remove residual wax, the solution was left in the freezer overnight and filtered one more time through a Millipore Express® PLUS membrane filter (polyethersulfone membrane, 0.22 μm). By this method, all the visually detectable wax

was removed. The solvent was evaporated in a vacuum evaporator (200 rpm) at 30 °C. The pure propolis sample was lyophilized to remove residual water. The dried extract was weighted to get yield and finally stored in amber glass vials at 4 °C. From this point on, the term “propolis” or “PP” refers to the ethanolic extract of propolis used in the experiments, even if not explicitly stated as “extract” in every instance.

2.4. Preparation of glucan particles

Glucan particles (GPs) were obtained from baker's yeast by a multi-step procedure, based on the work of Saloň et al. [37]. This procedure involves the removal of internal organelles by several steps: alkali extraction, acidification, and washing with deionized water, isopropanol, and acetone. Firstly, 150 g of dry baker's yeast was gradually poured into the 1M sodium hydroxide solution, mixed with T10 basic Ultra-Turrax (IKA), and stirred for 1 h at 90 °C. Then, the suspension was centrifuged (10,000 rpm, 3 min) and the supernatant was discarded. This alkali extraction was repeated two more times with a fresh 1M sodium hydroxide solution. The remaining sediment was resuspended in distilled water and by using 35% hydrochloride acid, the pH was adjusted to reach values between 4 and 5. The suspension was continuously stirred for 2 h at 75 °C. After 2 h, the supernatant was discarded and the sediment was resuspended, mixed, and centrifuged (7000 rpm, 10 min). These partial steps were repeated three times with deionized water, four times with isopropanol, and two times with acetone. The final product was left in a fume hood for acetone evaporation to obtain a dry powder, which was then lyophilized for 48 h, and stored in a refrigerator, protected from air humidity.

2.5. Encapsulation by spray drying

Propolis (at a ratio of 1:9 with respect to GPs) was dissolved in ethanol. GPs were then added to the solution, and the resulting suspension was homogenized using T10 basic Ultra-Turrax (IKA). The volume of used ethanol was calculated to achieve the final concentration 20 mg/mL of GPs in suspension. The initial loading of propolis extract was set to 10 wt % relative to the total mass of the formulation. This value was selected as a starting point based on literature data [26], suggesting that such a loading is likely to ensure complete encapsulation of the active compound. The spray drying was performed on a Mini Spray Dryer B-290 (Büchi AG, Switzerland) with an ultrasonic nozzle under a nitrogen atmosphere. The process parameters, set according to the work of Ruphuy et al. [26], were: inlet gas temperature 120 °C, flow rate of the suspension 5 mL/min, ultrasonic nozzle set to 2.4 W, outlet gas temperature 70 °C. The final product, comprising dry propolis-loaded glucan particles, was stored in a refrigerator. Further studies with higher propolis loading will be considered if sufficient encapsulation efficiency and promising biological activity are observed.

2.6. Encapsulation by rotary evaporator

Similarly to the spray-drying method, the concentration of propolis (PP) was initially set to achieve 10 wt % loading in the final GPs/PP composites, to evaluate the feasibility of the encapsulation process, with the intention to increase the loading in case of favorable results. GPs (10 mg/mL) were added into the ethanolic solution of propolis, and the suspension was homogenized in a round bottom flask using T10 basic Ultra-Turrax (IKA). After the homogenization, the suspension was placed in a rotary evaporator. Ethanol was removed by slowly decreasing the pressure, starting from the atmospheric pressure up to 80 mbar, by setting the rotary evaporator to 175 rpm and the water bath heated to 60 °C. The resulting powder was lyophilized for 48 h to remove residual moisture.

2.7. Characterization of GPs/PP composites

GPs/PP composites, a material formed by combining glucan particles as a carrier and propolis as the active ingredient, were characterized based on their physicochemical properties.

2.7.1. Scanning electron microscopy

The surface morphology and shape of propolis extracts, empty GPs, and GPs/PP composites were studied by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Joel JCM-5700. Prior to the analysis, the samples were coated with a thin layer (~5 nm) of gold with an Emitech K550X.

2.7.2. Size distribution

The size distribution of GPs was evaluated by the laser scattering particle size distribution analyzer Horiba Partica LA-950V2. Before the measurement, GPs were dispersed in a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of distilled water and ethanol, and subjected to sonication.

2.7.3. X-ray powder diffraction

The crystallinity of propolis extracts, empty GPs, and GPs/PP composites was evaluated by powder X-ray diffraction using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO diffractometer with High Score Plus software. Scans were taken from 5° to 50° 2θ angle.

2.7.4. Attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

Characteristic bands of propolis extracts, empty GPs, and GPs/PP composites were identified by a Nicolet iZ10 FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared) module with Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR-FTIR) on a ZnSe crystal. The spectra were collected as 64 co-added scans in the range of 4000-700 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.7.5. Nitrogen sorption measurements

The nitrogen sorption, at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K), was measured to determine the specific area and pore distribution of empty GPs and GPs/PP composites. The specific area was evaluated by the BET method, and the pore diameters were calculated using BJH method from the desorption part of the isotherm. The measurements were carried out on a 3Flex 5.01 instrument from Micromeritics, USA.

2.8. Composition of propolis extracts and composites

2.8.1. Sample preparation

In the case of both PP and GPs samples, propolis extracts were prepared in methanol with a concentration of 10 mg/mL.

To evaluate the concentration, extracted ion chromatograms of 10x or 100x diluted extracts of these samples were used for the majority of monitored analytes, as needed, to ensure that the intensity of the evaluated analyte was within the range of the calibration curve for the given standard. GPs/PP composites were prepared independently in three separate batches and each sample was analyzed twice, to evaluate the homogeneity of the preparation process.

2.8.2. Instrumental condition

The chromatographic separation was performed using a Dionex UltiMate 3000 RS UHPLC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) with a reversed-phase BEH C18 column (2.1 × 100 mm, 1.8 μm particle size, Waters, USA) at 60 °C. The mobile phase consisted of 5 mM ammonium formate and 0.1 % formic acid in (A) water/methanol (95/5, v/v) and (B) isopropanol/methanol/water (65/30/5, v/v/v) with a gradient elution: 0–2 min 90 % (A), 2–7 min 50–20 % (A), 7–13 min 20–0 % (A), 13–22 min 0 % (A), 22–22.1 min 0–90 % (A), 22.1–24 min 90 % (A). The mobile phase flow rate was 0.4 mL/min and the sample injection volume was 2 μL.

Mass spectrometric detection was performed using a TripleTOF 6600 instrument (SCIEX, Canada) equipped with a Duo Spray with a separated ESI ion source and atmospheric-pressure chemical ionization (APCI). ESI

was used for the measurement of extracts of the sample and APCI was used for the exact mass calibration of the instrument. The parameters of the ESI ion source were as follows: capillary voltage: +5000 V in ESI+ and - 4500 V in ESI-; collision energy 35 ± 15 V in ESI+ and $- 35 \pm 15$ V in ESI-; declustering potential: 80 V in ESI+ and - 80 V in ESI-; desolvation temperature: 480 °C; curtain gas: 35 psi; drying gas pressure: 55 psi and nebulizing gas pressure: 55 psi. TOF MS method and Information Dependent Acquisition (IDA) method were employed to record full MS and MS/MS spectra at the same time. The m/z range was between 100 and 1200 Da for MS and between 50 and 1200 Da for MS/MS. An automatic m/z calibration was performed on every 6 samples using an APCI Positive or Negative Calibration Solution. Analyst TF 1.7.1 software (SCIEX, Canada) was used for instrument control and data acquisition.

2.8.3. Targeted screening of biologically active compounds

SCIEX OS 1.5 software (SCIEX, Canada) was used for targeted screening of biologically active compounds. When a substance with a searched formula was detected in an extract of the sample (considering accurate mass, mass error, and isotopic pattern in MS), the measured MS/MS spectrum was compared to the literature and available databases such as PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), ChemSpider (<http://www.chemspider.com/>), mzCloud (<https://www.mzcloud.org/home>), or METLIN (<https://metlin.scripps.edu/index.php>). The internal database of these compounds was created using LibraryView 1.0.3. software (SCIEX, Canada) and was subsequently imported into the SCIEX OS 1.5 software (SCIEX, Canada). The formula, adduct, retention time, and MS/MS spectra were saved in this library. Data evaluation was performed using SCIEX OS 1.5 software (SCIEX, Canada).

In addition, standards of detected important substances were analyzed to confirm their identification and for their quantitative analysis. The identification was confirmed based on the agreement of the retention time and MS/MS fragmentation spectra. Quantification was performed based on measuring the exact m/z value, integrating the peak area, and using the external calibration of appropriate standards (0.005–10 µg/mL in ethanol).

2.9. Validation of UV–VIS spectrophotometric method

To evaluate linearity, standard stock solutions of the drug were prepared in a suitable solvent and serially diluted to obtain concentrations ranging from 1.2 to 31.7 mg/L. Each concentration was measured in triplicate using a UV–VIS spectrophotometer at the determined λ_{\max} . The Limit of Detection (LOD) and the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) were calculated based on statistical analysis of the linearity data. Blank glucan particles and solvent blanks were also analyzed to assess specificity. Precision was evaluated by intra-day repeatability across three concentration levels. For accuracy assessment, known amounts of drug were spiked into blank glucan particles and extracted using the same procedure applied to loaded samples. The extract was analyzed for recovery efficiency.

2.10. Encapsulation efficiency

To investigate the amount of propolis extract incorporated into GPs, GPs/PP composites (6 mg) were mixed with 25 mL of ethanol and subjected to ultrasonic extraction for 5, 10, and 30 min. A total of nine samples were analyzed, with three replicates for each sonication time. The aim was to compare the effectiveness of different extraction times in releasing propolis from GPs into the ethanolic medium and to identify the optimal extraction time.

Following this, GPs were separated by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 3 min. The centrifugation conditions (centrifugation speed and duration) were optimized based on preliminary experiments to ensure effective separation of the solid fraction (glucan particles) while

minimizing losses of the encapsulated propolis. Finally, the supernatant was filtered through a 25 mm syringe filter with 0.45 µm polyethersulfone membrane.

The concentration of propolis in the collected filtrate was quantified using a previously validated UV–VIS spectrophotometric method above (2.9 Validation of UV–VIS spectrophotometric method). Absorbance was at 316 nm using UV–VIS spectrophotometer Analytik Jena Specord 205 and the concentration was calculated according to the calibration curve in ethanol prepared from pure propolis extracts ($\lambda_{\text{abs}} = 316$ nm; y (PP 1) = $31.978x - 0.0042$, $R^2 = 0.9999$; y (PP 2) = $33.211x - 0.0086$, $R^2 = 0.9996$; y (PP 3) = $38.859x - 0.002$, $R^2 = 1$). The samples were measured in triplicate. The efficiency of the encapsulation process (EE) was calculated as follows:

$$EE (\%) = 100 \frac{\text{experimental content of propolis in GPs}}{\text{theoretical content of propolis in GPs}}$$

where the experimental content of propolis in GPs is the amount of extracted propolis from GPs into ethanol, and the theoretical content of propolis in GPs is the theoretical amount of propolis initially weighed before the encapsulation process.

2.11. Propolis release kinetics

The release kinetics of propolis was observed in two types of media. First dissolution tests were carried out in USP 2 (mini-paddle) apparatus coupled to UV–VIS spectrophotometer Specord 200 Plus (Analytik Jena, Germany), to immediately measure the rate and extent of release of propolis from GPs by measuring absorption at 316 nm. Each dissolution vessel was filled with 200 mL of phosphate buffer with pH 6.8 and pre-heated to 37 °C. Afterward, either propolis extracts or GPs/PP composites were placed into the media and continuously stirred (150 rpm). The GPs/PP composites' weight corresponded to the dose of 8 mg of propolis. Samples were collected at pre-defined time points (0–60 min) while filtered through 0.22 µm filters to separate the dissolved fraction from the propolis-loaded particles.

Further tests were intended to show dissolution rates under sink conditions. A standard 900 mL USP 2 (paddle) round-bottom dissolution vessels consisting of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) with the addition of 1 % sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were used. The media were maintained at 37 °C and stirred at 75 rpm. Approximately 36 mg of dose of crude or encapsulated propolis extracts were collected at pre-defined points (0–48 h), filtered through 0.22 µm filters, and measured on Lightwave II + UV–VIS spectrophotometer (Biochrom Ltd, England) at 316 nm. Final results were calculated according to the calibration curve in ethanol prepared from pure propolis extracts ($\lambda_{\text{abs}} = 316$ nm; y (PP 1) = $31.633x - 0.0006$, $R^2 = 0.9992$; y (PP 2) = $35.707x - 0.0036$, $R^2 = 0.999$; y (PP 3) = $28.802x - 0.0043$, $R^2 = 0.9996$). All measurements were carried out in triplicate.

2.12. In vitro testing

2.12.1. Sample preparation

To determine the effect of solvents on biological activities, the propolis extracts were dissolved in three different solvents - DMSO, ethanol, and cell cultivation medium. Stock solution of propolis in DMSO and ethanol was 100 g/L and maximum tested concentrations were 1 g/L, thus resulting in a final organic solvent concentration of 1 %. Stock solution of propolis in cell cultivation medium was prepared as saturated solution, the amount of propolis was determined spectrophotometrically using a propolis calibration curve. The highest tested concentration of propolis in the cultivation medium corresponded to a twice diluted saturated solution. The amount of propolis in GPs was calculated according to loading capacity. Both GPs and GPs/PP composites were dispersed in the test medium at a concentration of 20 g/L. Dissolution of was achieved by sonication for 5 min, in order to ensure

proper glucan particle dispersion before testing. The maximum tested concentration of GPs/PP composites was 2 g/L, which resulted in a test medium concentration of 1 %.

2.12.2. Cytotoxicity

The hTERT-immortalized epithelial proximal tubular cells (RPTEC/TERT1, CHT-003-0002Evercyte, Wien, Austria) were plated at a concentration of $1 \cdot 10^5$ cells/mL for 24 h in ProxUp2 medium (Evercyte). After that, the medium was replaced with a new one with the addition of tested substances. After 72 h, cell viability was measured by the resazurin test [43]. Briefly, the cells were incubated with resazurin solution (30 mg/L) for 30 min, then fluorescence was measured at 560/590 nm using a SpectraMax i3x Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, San Jose, CA, USA). The results were expressed as the percentage of viable cells relative to the untreated control.

2.12.3. Anti-inflammatory activity

Nitric oxide (NO) production and cytokine release (TNF α and IL-6) were quantified using RAW 264.7 cells (Merck, 91062702) according to the previously described method by Krížková et al. [44], briefly as follows. RAW 264.7 macrophages were stimulated with LPS (100 μ g/L) for 24 h, and NO production was quantified in the supernatant using the Griess reagent (0.04 g/mL) at a 1:1 ratio, with absorbance measured at 540 nm after 15 min of incubation. Cytokine levels in the supernatant were determined by ELISA, where the supernatant was incubated with capture antibodies coated onto 96-well plates, followed by incubation with biotinylated antibodies and signal development using streptavidin-horseradish peroxidase (HRP) and tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate. Concentrations of samples, that were cytotoxic, were excluded, see chapter 3.7.

2.12.4. Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity was quantified using RAW 264.7 cells. Cells were seeded at confluency overnight. After that, the medium was replaced with a medium enriched with 12.5 mg/L concentration of fluorescein and various concentrations of the tested substances (concentrations of samples, that were cytotoxic, were excluded, see chapter 3.7). After 1 h, the medium was replaced with a solution of 2,2'-Azobis (2-amidinopropane) dihydrochloride (AAPH) in PBS with a concentration of 16.3 mg/L. The fluorescence signal was read at 5-min intervals for 42 h.

The IC₅₀ values were calculated from a comparison of the guidelines according to the formula:

$$\text{Radical formation (\%)} = 100 \frac{\text{slope}_{\text{sample}} - \text{slope}_{\text{NC}}}{\text{slope}_{\text{PC}} - \text{slope}_{\text{NC}}},$$

where slope indicates the change of fluorescence over time. The AAPH solution was chosen as the positive control (PC) and the PBS solution as the negative control (NC).

2.12.5. Antimicrobial activity

Bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (DBM 7002) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (CCM 3955) cultivated in MH (Mueller Hinton, Merck) and yeast *Candida albicans* (DBM 2186) cultivated in MEA (Malt Extract Agar, Merck) were incubated overnight. Microbial cultures were then prepared according to ISO 20776-1. Then the cells were added to the plate with the test substances. After 24 h, the resazurin assay was used to test cell viability [43]. The fluorescence was measured at 544/590 nm using Fluoroskan Ascent FL (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

2.12.6. In vitro wound healing assay

The wound healing ability of propolis and encapsulated propolis was evaluated *in vitro* by scratch assay using keratinocytes (HaCaT, C0055C, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and expressed as the percentage of wound closure at different time intervals according to the previously described method [45]. In this work, HaCaT cells were seeded at the concentration of $1 \cdot 10^5$ cells/mL. The concentration of all tested samples was 5 mg/L. As a control, empty GPs and medium without samples were used. Scratch area images were captured at 24, 48, and 72 h.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical appearance of propolis and glucan particles

In this work, three different types of propolis, collected in Česká Lípa in 2018 (PP 1) and in Prague in the years 2020 (PP 2) and 2021 (PP 3) were used. These differ not only in physical appearance but also in composition and biological activity. Fig. 1 shows images of raw materials, so as materials after processing and lyophilization. All the raw propolis samples were dark and very sticky (Fig. 1A–C). Subsequent extraction effectively eliminated any visible wax while also improving the flowability of the final product. The final products differed in color;

Fig. 1. Images of: (A) raw PP 1, (B) raw PP 2, (C) raw PP 3, (D) baker's yeast, (E) PP 1 extract, (F) PP 2 extract, (G) PP 3 extract, (H) lyophilized GPs.

while PP 1 (Fig. 1E) was dark brown, PP 2 (Fig. 1F) was brighter, but still brown with orange shades, and PP 3 (Fig. 1G) had more shades of a yellow color.

The yield of GPs (Fig. 1H) was 6.88 ± 1.27 %, and of propolis extracts, prepared by our modified method, was: 48.64 % of PP 1, 56.84 % of PP 2, and 71.41 % of PP 3. Even though the same procedure was used for all types of propolis extracts, yield differences occurred, so it is certain that the initial content of wax and insoluble impurities has a great influence on product yield.

3.2. Characterization of GPs/PP composites

The physicochemical properties of the prepared GPs/PP composites were similar for all types of propolis extracts. For the purpose of brevity, some of the following paragraphs show only the data from PP 3 samples, whereas in these cases, the data from other samples (PP 1, PP 2) can be found in the Supplementary Information.

3.2.1. Scanning electron microscopy

The samples of propolis extract, empty GPs, and the encapsulated propolis in GPs by either spray drying or rotary evaporation were studied by scanning electron microscopy. Images are shown in Fig. 2. In all samples containing empty GPs (Fig. 2B), the SEM images showed the typical 2–4 μm ellipsoidal morphology with a wrinkled surface, caused by the hydrolysis of the outer cell wall of GPs and intracellular components, which is consistent with already published articles [26,40,46]. GPs loaded with PP 3 by spray drying (Fig. 2C) or rotary evaporation (Fig. 2D) did not reveal any significant difference compared to empty GPs, which may indicate that all the propolis is comprised in the GPs/PP composites and does not form any new structures. The appearance of other propolis extracts (PP 1, PP 2) was alike after loading in GPs (see Supplementary Information 1, Figs. S1 and S2). Similar results from the successful loading of natural active ingredient into GPs were reported by Šalamúnová et al. [33].

3.2.2. Size distribution

Particle size distribution of pure GPs was measured using laser diffraction in a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of water and ethanol to prevent excessive swelling, which occurs when the particles are dispersed in water. The GPs were then subjected to sonication during which agglomerates were disrupted into individual particles or smaller clusters, resulting in homogenous dispersion. The resulting volume based

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution of pure GPs.

Fig. 2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of (A) PP 3 extract, (B) empty GPs, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 3 composites, (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 3 composites. Scale bars represent (A) 100 μm , and (B, C, D) 10 μm .

histogram (Fig. 3) revealed a unimodal distribution with the majority of particles concentrated between 1.5 and 7 μm . The volume mean particle size of GPs determined by laser diffraction was $3.46 \pm 2.20 \mu\text{m}$. This relatively high variation suggests residual polydispersity, likely due to natural particle variability or minor aggregation. The D_{10} , D_{50} , D_{90} values were 1.51 μm , 2.98 μm , and 6.72 μm , respectively. The observed size range falls within values commonly reported for glucan particles in the literature [26,39].

3.2.3. X-ray powder diffraction

Empty GPs were found to be fully amorphous (Fig. 4A) when analyzed by XRPD. Both propolis extracts PP 3 (Fig. 4B) and PP 2 were amorphous, while only a small percentage of crystalline form was found in PP 1 (see Supplementary Information 2, Figs. S3 and S4). All propolis extracts loaded in GPs (see GPs/PP3 composites in Fig. 4C and D) were completely amorphous, which is expressed by a characteristic band at 20° .

Fig. 4. X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns of (A) pure GPs, (B) PP 3 extract, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 3 composites and (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 3 composites.

Fig. 5. Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectra of (A) pure GPs, (B) PP 3 extract, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 3 composites and (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 3 composites.

3.2.4. Attenuated total reflectance fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

ATR-FTIR is a frequently used method for a chemical structure characterization of GPs and their typical chemical groups per literature [47,48]. The characteristic bands for (1,3)- and/or (1,6)-linked β -glucans are 1160, 1078, 1041, and 889 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1160 cm^{-1} corresponds to COC and CC stretching vibrations. Absorption bands at 1070 cm^{-1} and 1040 cm^{-1} relate to the stretching vibrations of CO and CC. The band at 890 cm^{-1} belongs to β -glycosidic linkages (C1H). The reported region for propolis extract is between 1100 and 1800 cm^{-1} , which, associated with the CO group is ascribed to the flavonoids and lipids [28]. In all spectra (see Fig. 5 and Supplementary Information 3, Figs. S5 and S6), the peak in the area around 1550 cm^{-1} corresponded to propolis extract and confirmed successful loading.

3.2.5. Nitrogen sorption measurements

Nitrogen sorption measurements can provide detailed information on, for instance, the surface area or volume of pores. For this purpose, the empty GPs and GPs/PP were analyzed by this method, and the results are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 6. The empty GPs exhibited the highest specific surface area and volume of pores, with an average pore size of approximately 9 nm. This high porosity results from the removal of internal organelles and lyophilization drying process during the preparation which are crucial for their functionality in efficiently encapsulating and also releasing the particular active ingredient making them a promising candidate for drug delivery systems. After the encapsulation of propolis extracts into the porous structure of GPs, we observe a decrease in both surface area and pore volume, which is primarily caused by propolis extracts filling the pores.

3.3. Validation of UV-VIS spectrophotometric method

The UV-VIS spectrophotometric method showed linearity over the

Table 1
Nitrogen sorption measurements of specific surface area and desorption total pore volume of pores of empty GPs and GPs/PP composites.

	BET surface (m^2/g)	Pore volume (mm^3/g)
GPs	77.54	189.63
GPs/PP 1	30.97	100.00
GPs/PP 2	33.96	124.55
GPs/PP 3	33.68	110.52

Fig. 6. Barrett, Joyner & Halenda (BJH) desorption pore distribution of empty GPs and GPs/PP composites.

tested concentration range ($R^2 = 0.999$). The regression equation was $y = 0.0343x + 0.1895$. Precision testing resulted in % RSD values ranging from 0.33 % to 0.47 %, indicating consistent performance. Accuracy values ranged from 95 % to 99 % recovery with % RSD values below 5 %, which meets the acceptance criteria defined in ICH Q2(R2) guidelines [49]. The LOD and LOQ were calculated as 1.49 mg/L and 4.50 mg/L, respectively, with LOQ corresponding to an absorbance of 0.34 AU. The evaluation of LOD and LOQ reflects standard validation practices documented in the literature [50,51]. These results confirm that the method is suitable for quantifying drug loading in GPs with acceptable sensitivity, accuracy, and reproducibility.

3.4. Encapsulation efficiency

The content of propolis encapsulated in GPs was evaluated by ethanol extraction, determined by UV–VIS spectrophotometry, calculated according to the equation described in the chapter 2.10, and is presented in Fig. 7. The spectrum of raw propolis has two characteristic peaks with local maxima at 294 nm and 316 nm, whereas GPs also absorb at the wavelength of 290 nm. The spectra are provided in Supplementary Information 4, Fig. S7. Because of this spectral overlap, quantification of propolis was performed at 316 nm, where the absorbance is more specific to propolis and less affected by GPs. In the absence of GPs, propolis can also be determined at 290 nm.

To optimize the ethanol extraction procedure, different sonication times (5, 10, and 30 min) were tested. The measured concentrations of propolis extracted after 5, 10, and 30 min were comparable, indicating no significant increase in yield occurred beyond 5 min. This suggests that a 10 min sonication is sufficient to achieve complete release of the encapsulated propolis from GPs. Therefore, 10 min was selected as the optimal compromise between extraction efficiency and processing time for all ethanol extraction experiments.

UV–VIS spectrophotometry was selected because the system under study is a complex multi-component natural mixture. The aim of the analysis was not to separate and quantify individual components, as would be typical for UHPLC analysis, but rather to determine the total amount of propolis extract released from the particles. For this purpose, the analyte was considered as the whole extract, and UV–VIS provided sufficient sensitivity and reliability. Moreover, since biological activity is the focus of this work, it is important to highlight that active compounds act synergistically as a mixture, which is characteristic of natural products like propolis. Thus, the measured total propolis extract

corresponds to the biologically active mixture responsible for the observed activity.

In addition to UV–VIS quantification, UHPLC methanolic fingerprint analysis was performed (see Supplementary Information 6, Fig. S9) to confirm the completeness of propolis encapsulation. The UHPLC profiles showed characteristic peaks of propolis in the encapsulated samples, supporting the reliability of the UV–VIS method and indicating minimal loss.

For all samples, the initial loading of propolis extract in the GPs was targeted to 10 wt %, based on literature data [26], which suggests that this concentration is optimal for ensuring complete encapsulation. However, the theoretical content of propolis used for calculating encapsulation efficiency was determined individually for each sample based on the exact mass of propolis extract added during the specific encapsulation process (the theoretical content of propolis in GPs).

Two encapsulation methods were compared: spray drying and rotary evaporation. Although incorporation in rotary evaporator resulted in higher yields (88.49 % for PP 1, 80.89 % for PP 2, and 86.86 % for PP 3), compared to spray drying (48.91 % for PP 1, 49.73 % for PP 2, and 49.71 % for PP 3), the encapsulation efficiencies were significantly better with spray drying (Fig. 7). The lower encapsulation efficiencies, obtained using a rotary evaporator, could be attributed to insufficient encapsulation, which was visually observed during the process as sticking of the propolis to the used equipment. In addition, after encapsulation of propolis by spray drying, the powder was uniform, fine, and with good flowability, whereas rotary evaporated samples were less homogenous. For these reasons, our following work proceeded with only spray-dried composites.

Additionally, the percentage of the actual loading of the propolis extract was evaluated for each encapsulation method and each propolis type. For spray drying, the loadings were: 8.61 ± 0.12 % for PP 1, 9.86 ± 0.09 % for PP 2, and 8.62 ± 0.24 % for PP 3. In comparison, rotary evaporation resulted in lower loadings: 6.36 ± 0.20 % for PP 1, 6.28 ± 0.12 % for PP 2, and 6.11 ± 0.16 % for PP 3. All values were determined in triplicate and are reported as mean \pm standard deviation. These results confirm the technological advantage of spray drying not only in terms of encapsulation efficiency but also in terms of the loading. The improved loading can be attributed to better process control and reduced material losses during drying, as propolis visibly adhered to equipment surfaces during rotary evaporation.

3.5. Composition of propolis extracts and composites

The diverse chemical composition inherent to different propolis types makes characterizing its full chemical profile a significant challenge. To effectively manage this complexity, we selected eight standards, including chrysin, apigenin, kaempferol, quercetin, pinocembrin, galangin, 10-hydroxyl-2-decenoic acid, and cinnamic acid, which are among the most commonly represented and pharmacologically active substances found in propolis samples mainly across Europe. According to their geographical origin and the presence of these typical chemical compounds, it is assumed that the botanical origin belongs to the genus *Populus* [52–54].

The use of ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) enabled us to quantify these compounds, which is crucial in understanding how the composition affects the therapeutic potential of these bioactive compounds. Our analyses revealed that 10-hydroxyl-2-decenoic acid and cinnamic acid were not detected in the samples (<5 and $10 \mu\text{g/g}$). The data presented in Fig. 8 show that galangin, chrysin, and pinocembrin were predominant in the propolis samples, consistent with other studies [1,53,55,56]. This finding also correlates with the known chemical profiles of propolis from similar geographical regions. The high content of these bioactive compounds highlights the potential health benefits, particularly antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects. However, the overall complexity of propolis makes it difficult to attribute the activity to a single molecule, which is explained

Fig. 7. Encapsulation efficiency (EE) of propolis extracts (PP) after encapsulation by spray drying (solid fill) and rotary evaporation (downward diagonal). spray dried GPs/PP 1; rotary evaporated GPs/PP 1, spray dried GPs/PP 2, rotary evaporated GPs/PP 2, spray dried GPs/PP 3, rotary evaporated GPs/PP 3. The error bars represent the standard deviation ($n = 3$).

Fig. 8. Concentration of chrysin, apigenin, kaempferol, quercetin, pinocembrin, and galangin in propolis extracts; PP1; PP2, PP3. 10-hydroxyl-2-decenoic acid and cinnamic acid were not detected in the samples. The error bars represent the standard deviation ($n = 2$).

by the possible synergy between the components [57].

Furthermore, to verify that all the substances contained in the propolis get inside the glucan particles during the encapsulation process, methanolic fingerprints of propolis extracts and GPs/PP composites, in positive and negative electrospray ionization modes, were measured and compared. Worth noticing is that according to the individual signals (chromatographic peaks) in the chromatographic records (see Supplementary Information 6, Fig. S9), it is evident that the transfer of substances from propolis to glucan particles, i.e. encapsulation, is qualitatively non-selective. This means that all propolis substances have been encapsulated in GPs. On the other hand, the encapsulation process is not quantitative, which is indicated by the different ratios of some compounds in GP/PP composites in comparison to propolis extracts.

3.6. Dissolution tests

Dissolution profiles shown in Fig. 9 were obtained in a phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 for propolis extracts and GPs/PP composites prepared by spray drying with a propolis dose of 8 mg. We performed the study in conditions without SDS to assess the ability of propolis to create a supersaturated solution, which can improve bioavailability. Moreover, it helps to evaluate a dissolution behavior without interference. This ensures that the results reflect the propolis's natural properties rather than being influenced by surfactants, which could artificially enhance solubility.

There was a significant improvement in the dissolution rate in the case of all propolis types after their loading into GPs relative to the propolis extracts alone. Regarding propolis extracts, dissolution profiles had a similar course for all tested samples (Fig. 9). A small portion dissolved within the first 5 min, and then the dissolution slowed down, with the total dissolved fraction not exceeding 10 % over the course of 60 min. There were slight differences between the final dissolved fractions, where the PP 1 released fraction was almost 8 %, which corresponds to 3.13 ± 0.23 mg/L. Propolis that was released the least, nearly 4 % (1.52 ± 0.34 mg/L), was PP 2. The variety of reached concentrations could be caused by differences in propolis extract composition.

A significant increase in the dissolution rate of all propolis samples was observed after the encapsulation into GPs (Fig. 9). GPs/PP 2 composites manifested the lowest release. This curve differed from others because in just 5 min, the medium became supersaturated and at this point, the concentration of active ingredient was at the highest peak and

Fig. 9. Dissolution kinetics of propolis extracts and spray-dried GPs/PP composites in 200 mL media (pH 6.8) at 37 °C and mini-paddles set as 150 rpm; PP 1; PP 2; PP 3; GPs/PP 1; GPs/PP 2; GPs/PP 3. The error bars represent the standard deviation ($n = 3$).

decreased from then on, which is attributed to the precipitation. After the first 15 min, the concentration of PP 2 released from GPs was 9.12 ± 0.80 mg/L and remained relatively stable throughout the rest of the dissolution test. The final concentration of PP 2 corresponds to almost 23 % of the dose. On the other hand, the remaining two composites, GPs/PP 1 and GPs/PP 3 behaved quite alike. In both cases, there was rapid release in the first 5 min, which then decelerated, but the total concentration continued to increase. After 25–30 min, the composites reached the solubility limit and remained constant. PP 1 encapsulated in GPs has achieved the highest solubility (16.27 ± 1.96 mg/L) and about 41 % of the dose was dissolved.

Moreover, encapsulation in GPs improves dispersion of the composites even without surfactant, which helps hydrophobic drugs with poor dispersibility to increase their solubility in polar media as was proved also in the study of Ruphuy et al. [26].

Dissolution profiles shown in Fig. 10 were performed with the same samples (propolis extracts, GPs/PP composites) as in dissolution tests before (Fig. 9) with the dose of 36 mg and with the addition of 1 % surfactant (SDS) to achieve sink conditions, allowing for dissolving the whole dose. For propolis solubility, see Supplementary Information 5, Fig. S8. PP 2 and PP3 extracts dissolved completely over the course of the experiment, reaching the maximum measured concentration at 48 h with the final measured concentrations of 40.65 ± 0.76 mg/L and 41.41 ± 1.22 mg/L, respectively. The concentration of propolis released from the PP 1 extract at 48 h was only 31.66 ± 3.45 mg/L with the dissolution profile indicating that the concentration would likely continue to grow if measured after a longer time period. The differences in the dissolution rates of the pure extracts can be possibly attributed to the different chemical compositions of the samples indicated by the UHPLC measurements (Supplementary Information 6, Fig. S9).

The encapsulation of propolis into GPs significantly enhanced the dissolution rate when compared to pure propolis extracts. In the case of all composites, most of the propolis dissolved already within the first hour of the dissolution experiment. The composites exhibited differences during the initial phase of the test, specifically in the first 30 min, where the GP/PP 1 composites released the propolis the fastest and GPs/PP 3 the slowest. After 1 h, all three profiles converged, showing similar dissolution rates for the remainder of the study period. By the 48 h mark, all composites had dissolved about 90 % of the propolis, specifically 93 % of the dose was dissolved from GPs/PP 1 (37.29 ± 0.70 mg/L) and GPs/PP 2 (37.29 ± 1.40 mg/L) composites and 87 % (34.68 ± 0.34 mg/L) from GPs/PP 3 composites.

Fig. 10. Dissolution kinetics of propolis extracts and spray-dried GPs/PP composites in 900 mL media (pH 6.8) with 1 % of SDS at 37 °C and paddles set as 75 rpm; PP 1; PP 2; PP 3; GPs/PP 1; GPs/PP 2; GPs/PP 3. The error bars represent the standard deviation (n = 3).

3.7. In vitro bioactivity

The following set of experiments aimed to demonstrate that GPs/PP composites increase the bioactivity of propolis extracts and thus these propolis extracts become more biologically effective. As will be described in more detail below, GPs/PP composites show similar biological properties to propolis dissolved in 100 % DMSO, which is, however, inadmissible to the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries. The biological activity of GPs was further compared with propolis dissolved in ethanol, as this is a common solvent used in laboratory practice.

GPs/PP composites were shown to be safe for human cells at a concentration below 40 mg/L for GPs/PP 3 and 90 mg/L for GPs/PP 1 and GPs/PP 2 (Fig. 11A). At the same time, at these concentrations, they exhibited significant biological activities, especially anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial, and facilitated wound healing. Propolis encapsulated in GPs showed the same or higher biological activity compared to propolis in organic solvents. On the other hand, the propolis dissolved in the culture medium to a saturated state did not show significant biological activity, which is probably due to its low aqueous solubility. The encapsulation of propolis into GPs thus demonstrably increased its bioavailability and its potential application in the dermo-cosmetic industry.

3.7.1. Cytotoxicity

In order to determine the propolis safety in various solvents and in encapsulated form, a cytotoxicity test was performed on primary human renal tubular epithelial cells (HRTEC) after 72 h of incubation with the tested substances. In this work, empty GPs did not affect cell viability even at a concentration of 2 g/L (see Supplementary Information 7, Table S1). This is in agreement with a study by Lee et al. [58] where no cytotoxic effects of GPs were observed using human endothelial cells (HUVEC) at the maximum tested concentration of 1 g/L.

Fig. 11A shows the result of the cytotoxicity evaluation using HRTEC cells. The propolis extracts dissolved in the medium did not affect the cell viability within the tested range. The highest tested concentration of propolis in the medium corresponds to a 50 % saturated solution. Saturated solution concentration are: PP 1 is 0.258 ± 0.017 mg/mL, PP 2 0.449 ± 0.018 mg/mL, and PP 3 0.122 ± 0.006 mg/mL. The symbol “>” indicates the results where the expected IC_{50} value lies above the highest tested concentration. Propolis extracts solubilized in ethanol were less toxic than the same extracts solubilized in DMSO. GPs/PP had similar toxicity as DMSO-solubilized propolis extracts, except for PP 1, where encapsulation in GPs significantly increased the toxicity (see Fig. 11A and Table S1 in Supplementary Information 7).

3.7.2. Anti-inflammatory activity

The anti-inflammatory effect of propolis extracts, empty GPs

(Supplementary Information 7, Table S2), and GPs/PP composites were tested using LPS-stimulated RAW 264.7 macrophages as the ability to reduce cytokines and NO production. NO production (Fig. 11B) was significantly reduced by all propolis formulations. In all cases, ethanolic extracts were better than propolis solubilized in the cultivation medium. In the case of PP 1 and PP 3, dissolution in ethanol significantly increased their effect even compared to dissolution in DMSO. While empty GPs had no effect (Supplementary Information 7, Table S2), the encapsulation of propolis into GPs significantly increased the anti-inflammatory activity when compared to propolis solubilized in the cultivation medium. This effect was comparable to the usage of organic solvents. The inhibition of NO production by propolis was already found in a previous study by Búfalo et al. [59], where the anti-inflammatory activity was correlated with the caffeic acid content in the propolis (not quantified in this work).

Solubilization of propolis extracts in ethanol demonstrated significantly higher anti-inflammatory activity than in DMSO; therefore, measurement of cytokines release was limited only to ethanol and cultivation medium (Fig. 11C). In previous studies, propolis has already shown an effect on cytokine release. For example, in a study Kofuji et al. [60], an ethanol extract of Brazilian propolis significantly reduced the release of $TNF\alpha$ at a concentration of 10 mg/L. In this study, PP 1 and PP 2 showed a significant reduction in $TNF\alpha$ release only in the GPs encapsulated form. Neither propolis dissolved in ethanol nor in a cultivation medium was able to reduce $TNF\alpha$ production. In accordance with our previous data, the formulation of propolis into GPs was the most effective form of application, although, in the case of GPs/PP 2 and GPs/PP 3, this formulation was as effective as dissolving the propolis extract in an organic solvent.

Despite the fact that empty GPs did not interfere with $TNF\alpha$ content (Supplementary Information 7, Table S3), they significantly reduced the amount of released IL-6 ($IC_{50} = 166.1 \pm 12.9$ mg/L; Supplementary Information 7, Table S4). According to a study of Bastos et al. [61], β -glucans themselves should have the potential for pharmacological use. In this study, we demonstrated the anti-inflammatory potential of β -glucans in the reduction of IL-6 release. The extent of these effects may be influenced by the structure of the β -glucans. Structures of β -glucans have a significant effect on the chemical and physical properties, including the ability to activate and inhibit macrophage receptors [61].

Glucan particles interact with several immune receptors, such as Dectin-1 receptors, complement receptor 3 (CR3), and Toll-like receptors 2 (TLR-2) [34]. By this interaction, GPs transport substances into the cells. In the study of Sun et al. [62], the Dectin-1 and CR3 receptor-blocking antibodies were used to demonstrate the reduced uptake of GPs. In the same study, GPs-encapsulated methotrexate increased its anti-inflammatory activity and reduced its toxicity. In this study, propolis encapsulated in GPs/PP reduced the production of the inflammatory cytokine IL-6 more effectively than propolis dissolved in

Fig. 11. Bioactivity assays of three types of propolis (grey upward diagonal PP 1; purple dashed horizontal PP 2; red horizontal PP 3) in organic media (“DMSO”; “Ethanol”), cell culture media (“Media”) and encapsulated in glucon particles and dispersed in media (“GPs/PP”). Concentration of propolis samples halving (A) the viability (IC₅₀) of primary human renal tubular epithelial cells (HRTEC; cytotoxicity), production of (B) NO (anti-inflammatory), (C) TNFα (anti-inflammatory) and (D) IL-6 (anti-inflammatory) by LPS-stimulated macrophages (RAW 264.7), (E) the free radicals in macrophages RAW 264.7 after addition of 2,2'-Azobis(2-amidinopropane) dihydrochloride (AAPH) in PBS (antioxidant), the minimum inhibition concentration (MIC) of (F) *Candida albicans* (antimicrobial), (G) *Staphylococcus aureus* (antimicrobial), (H) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (antimicrobial). Values represent mean (n = 3) ± SEM. Symbol “>” indicates the results, where the expected IC₅₀/MIC value lies above the highest tested concentration. The highest tested concentration of propolis in the medium corresponds to 50 % of its saturated solution. The resulting values IC₅₀/MIC were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan’s *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$, where each letter above the bar indicates the group of samples which behave similarly. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the medium. Moreover, its effects were comparable to those of propolis dissolved in ethanol (Fig. 11D).

3.7.3. Antioxidant activity

Furthermore, cellular antioxidant activity (CAA) was tested using a probe, which after penetration through the cell wall, deacetylation, and subsequent oxidation in contact with radicals produces fluorescent 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein (DCF). Antioxidant activity was detected in all cases of both organic solvents used for propolis extracts solubilization apart from the PP 1 sample in DMSO (Fig. 11E). Interestingly, the antioxidant activity of PP 1 extract was remarkably improved after encapsulation in GPs; however, it was the only case where the encapsulation improved the antioxidant properties of propolis extract. On the contrary, encapsulation of PP 2 and PP 3 resulted in a loss of efficacy at non-toxic concentrations.

The influence of the origin of propolis on its bioactivity has been described earlier in the study by Kumazawa et al. [63], where it was found that European and Chinese propolis are far better antioxidants than Brazilian propolis. In our case, all propolis extracts were from the Czech Republic, but it seems that their antioxidant activity differs significantly. PP 2 and PP 3, which are from Prague, were better antioxidants than PP 1, which is from Česká Lípa. The observed differences might therefore be explained by variations in the local flora.

Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects of propolis are usually attributed to caffeic acid and other active substances contained in propolis, principally to flavonoids [64]. Different mechanisms of their antioxidant activity have been described. For example, quercetin (highest content measured in PP 3), should chelate iron ions [65]. Furthermore, it has been shown that some flavonoids induce the expression of enzymes that are responsible for the antioxidant defense of the cell. This was observed, for example, with naringin in the study Mamdouh and Monira [66]. In contrast the work by Mamdouh and Monira, where empty GPs had no antioxidant effect, Kofuji et al. [60] demonstrated that the β -glucans from barley showed antioxidant activity. However, this could be caused by the composition, where barley particles are mainly represented by β -(1,3-1,4)-D-glucans. In our work, empty GPs had no antioxidant effect (Supplementary Information 7, Table S5).

3.7.4. Antimicrobial activity

During the testing of the antimicrobial activity of propolis extracts and GPs, the effect on the viability of the yeast *Candida albicans* (Fig. 11F, Supplementary Information 7, Table S6), the Gram-positive

bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (Fig. 11G, Supplementary Information 7, Table S7), and the Gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Fig. 11H, Supplementary Information 7, Table S8) were evaluated. All propolis extracts dissolved in DMSO or ethanol demonstrated an effect on the viability of *C. albicans*, while there was no effect observed when the propolis was dissolved in the medium (Fig. 11F). GPs-encapsulated propolis demonstrated a significantly increased antimicrobial effect compared to all propolis extracts dissolved in organic solvents.

Propolis extracts (PP2 and PP3) dissolved in organic solvents exhibited a good antibacterial effect on both *S. aureus* (Fig. 11G) and *P. aeruginosa* (Fig. 11H) but the samples dissolved in the medium did not exhibit antibacterial activity in our experiments. However, the encapsulation of PP 3 into GPs improved its efficiency against *S. aureus*, highlighting the potential of these composites in the treatment of dermal bacterial infections even at extremely low concentrations.

In the study by Shah et al. [67], they encapsulated the flavonoid rutin in β -glucans while testing the antimicrobial effects on the gram-positive *S. aureus* and the gram-negative *Escherichia coli*. Encapsulated rutin had significantly less antimicrobial effects on *E. coli*. Also, Chamidah et al. [68] concluded that empty β -glucans have better effects against gram-positive bacteria, which is, however, not supported by our data as no antibacterial effect of empty GPs was observed here (Supplementary Information 7, Table S7). It is presumed that the effects should be influenced by the composition of the bacterial cell wall. In gram-positive cells, the integrity of the peptidoglycan chains should be disrupted and subsequently followed by cell lysis [68]. In this work, the effect of empty GPs was not observed even with gram-positive bacteria but a significant increase in the effect of propolis after its encapsulation was observed.

In the study of Pepeljnjak et al. [69], they compared three samples of raw propolis collected from Croatia. Their results showed high antibacterial activity against multi-resistant bacterial strains *S. aureus* (MIC = 0.16 ± 0.03 mg/mL) and *P. aeruginosa* (MIC = 0.17 ± 0.05 mg/mL). They showed that the ethanolic extracts with the highest galangin content has the strongest activity against anti-multi-drug resistant bacteria. So they attributed the activity to the content of the galangin. In our data, galangin was predominant in all propolis samples, especially in PP 3 (Fig. 8). PP 3 also exhibited good antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* when dissolved in ethanol (MIC = 0.27 ± 0.03 mg/L), but most importantly the highest activity when encapsulated in GPs (MIC = 0.011 ± 0.001 mg/L), see Fig. 11G – red horizontal, which is in agreement with the previously mentioned study.

Table 2

Screening for wound healing ability of propolis was performed using HaCaT by *in vitro* scratch assay, the response was recorded as the percentage of wound closure at different time intervals (24, 48 and 72 h).

	IC ₁₀ (µg/mL)	Wound closure (%)		
		24 h	48 h	72 h
			DMEM	
Control 1		54.1 ± 9.1	71.2 ± 7.9	86.7 ± 6.3
PP 1	5	72.1 ± 7.0 ***	78.3 ± 9.5 ***	100.0 ± 0.0 ***
PP 2	5	78.8 ± 4.7 ***	88.7 ± 4.5 ***	100.0 ± 0.0 ***
PP 3	5	81.2 ± 4.9 ***	86.4 ± 5.4 ***	100.0 ± 0.0 ***
			Ethanol	
PP 1	5	61.3 ± 6.0 ***	76.0 ± 6.2 *	89.2 ± 4.5 *
PP 2	5	55.1 ± 8.5 ns	77.8 ± 7.0 ***	80.3 ± 6.5 **
PP 3	5	56.1 ± 4.9 ns	80.5 ± 4.5 ***	88.6 ± 4.0 ns
			Glucan particles	
Control 2	5	57.7 ± 7.6 ***	75.0 ± 7.1 ***	87.0 ± 4.1 *
PP 1	5	78.5 ± 6.2 ***/###	90.4 ± 2.2 ***/###	100.0 ± 0.0 ***/###
PP 2	5	65.6 ± 6.7 ***/###	87.6 ± 3.0 ***/###	100.0 ± 0.0 ***/###
PP 3	5	86.2 ± 4.0 ***/###	100.0 ± 0.0 ***/###	–

The data here represents the average of twenty-five replicates with corresponding standard error of the mean. The data was analyzed with *t*-test (two tailed, *t*-test with unequal variance), the significance level between different data groups with the control 1 (only media) is represented as ns - not significant, **p* ≤ 0.05, ***p* ≤ 0.01, ****p* ≤ 0.001, and with control 2 (empty GPs) is represented as ns - not significant, #*p* ≤ 0.05, ##*p* ≤ 0.01, ###*p* ≤ 0.001.

3.8. *In vitro* wound healing assay

To study the effect of propolis on wound healing, we tested all the propolis extracts at a without possible non-toxic concentration, representing IC₁₀ (corresponding to 5 µg/mL) as displayed in Table 2. This concentration was used to observe the effects of a propolis on cell migration without causing significant cytotoxicity or affecting cell viability.

In the first 24 h of the experiment, the percentage of wound closure with propolis samples dissolved in ethanol ranged between 55 and 61 %. In contrast, the GPs/PP composites and propolis extracts dissolved in media ranged between 72–81 % and 66–86 % wound closure, respectively.

After 48 h, the closure rate of the propolis in ethanol ranged between 76 and 81 %, whereas the GPs/PP composites and propolis extracts dissolved in media exhibited closure rates of around 88–100 % and 78–89 %, respectively.

By 72 h, both the GPs/PP composites and propolis extracts dissolved in media demonstrated complete wound closure. Conversely, the propolis dissolved in ethanol only exhibited a maximum of 89 % closure, similar to the closure rate of control 1 (untreated cells).

Notably, the ethanolic solutions failed to achieve complete wound closure within the study period. The wound closure rate of propolis in ethanol was almost similar to control 1. Furthermore, control 2 (empty GPs) exhibited wound closure patterns similar to control 1, indicating that the GPs have minimal effect on wound closure when empty.

Out of all the propolis tested, PP 3 showed excellent wound healing ability. Specifically, the GPs/PP 3 composites manifested 100 % closure within 48 h. Additionally, the PP 3 extract dissolved in media also exhibited 100 % closure within 72 h (Fig. 12). PP 1 and PP 2 extracts exhibited lower wound healing ability compared to PP 3; however, both the encapsulated propolis and propolis extracts PP 1 and PP 2 dissolved in media achieved complete closure within 72 h. Images from an inverted microscope showing the ability of PP 1 and PP 2 to promote wound healing, as well as the effect of empty GPs, can be found in

Supplementary Information 8.

These findings suggest that wound healing promotion by propolis is a synergistic action of its antimicrobial, cytotoxic, and immunomodulatory properties, aiding in tissue repair and contraction. Notably, PP 3 displayed exceptional antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory abilities, correlating with its composition analysis (Fig. 8), where the concentration of substances responsible for these activities was highest.

4. Conclusion

To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to use glucan particles (GPs) as carriers for successful encapsulation of propolis. By combining these two natural materials, the broad bioactivity spectrum of propolis was amplified and extended, which can be attributed to the combination of GP's solubilization effect and synergy between the biological activity of GPs and propolis. These new findings support not just anti-inflammatory but also antioxidant and antimicrobial potential *in vitro* and enable the subsequent possibility of propolis' direct application. The anti-inflammatory activity of propolis extracts was increased after being loaded in GPs and was comparable to propolis extracts that were dissolved in an organic solvent. Antioxidant activity was detectable only in some organic solvents and after encapsulation in GPs. Encapsulation into GPs significantly improved the effect against the yeast *Candida albicans* and the gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus*. On the contrary, it had no effect on gram-negative bacterium *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. All propolis extracts exhibited excellent wound healing ability while encapsulated in GPs and dissolved directly in medium and manifesting 100 % wound closure within 72 h. On the other hand, propolis extracts dissolved in ethanol did not complete the closure of wound within the study period. Out of all tested samples, propolis 3 (PP 3) encapsulated in glucan particles (GPs/PP 3) even showed 100 % closure within 48 h. Since we produced completely amorphous composites of GPs with up to 10 wt % of propolis, it leads us to speculate that higher loading may contribute to even greater biological activity.

Fig. 12. Wound healing of propolis 3 extract dissolved in organic medium (“Ethanol”), cell culture medium (“DMEM”), and encapsulated in glucan particles (“GPs/PP 3”) and dissolved in cell culture medium (DMEM) at different time intervals (24, 48 and 72 h). Scale bars represent 200 µm.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adéla Brejchová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Eva Králová:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Ondřej Strnad:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Petra Trešňáková:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Giyauallah Habibullah:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Jana Rýparová Kvirencová:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Vojtěch Hrbek:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Jitka Viktorová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Denisa Lizoňová:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **František Štěpánek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2025.107490>.

Data availability

Research data for this article are available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17094808>.

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